

ASSESSMENT OF THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SEDIMENTS IN THE ORISA RIVER, Omu-ARAN, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Physicochemical parameters are naturally occurring substances found in the Earth's crust; an excessive amount of them in soil or water can be detrimental to both the environment and human health. There is little information about the assessment of sediments available in Omu-Aran, Nigeria. This study is aimed at determining the level of physicochemical contamination of sediments in Orisa River, Omu Aran, Nigeria. A total of 30 sediment samples were collected from five different sampling locations along the river, including a control station, over three weeks to determine the level of contamination by physicochemical parameters. The physicochemical parameters of the sediment samples were obtained by applying the standard methods. The analysis of data was achieved using descriptive statistics and ANOVA. The mean values of parameters in the soil samples from various sampling points varied from: 0.01 ± 0.00 and 2.94 ± 0.06 mg/L, 0.43 ± 0.03 to 2.73 ± 0.04 mg/L, 0.13 ± 0.03 to 1.6 ± 0.21 d mg/L, 11.83 ± 1.72 to 28.17 ± 1.72 mg/L, 8.71 ± 0.04 to 1.45 ± 0.29 mg/L, 12.42 ± 0.03 to 2.76 ± 0.07 , 27.77 ± 0.05 to 27.13 ± 0.05 for magnesium, nitrate, Phosphate, chloride, total dissolved solid, Electrical conductivity, temperature respectively. The results from the study also showed significant differences in the various parameters, except for temperature, and they were within the WHO regulatory standards. The Activities within the Orisa River do not harm the sediments in the River. It was then recommended that periodic monitoring and assessment of water and sediments in the study area be carried out (for preservation of this natural resource).

Keywords
Physicochemical
Parameters,
Sediments, Orisa
River

1. INTRODUCTION

Beyond any doubt, one of the most significant natural resources on Earth is water, and life is dependent upon it [1]. Water bodies that are easily accessible for domestic use, such as lakes, rivers, and springs, are quickly contaminated by pollutants primarily caused by human activity, and this degrades the water's quality [2]. Mining, industry, housing, and agricultural practices (including the use of fertilizers and pesticides) are the main sources of pollution in most rivers because they change the chemical and physical properties of water bodies [1,3]. The majority of developing nations see significant variations in water quality as a result of faeces polluting waterways, agricultural runoff, and laundry. Sediment treatment and collection in the majority of emerging nations typically do not keep pace with population expansion [4]. One can test for nutrients in the water by looking at its pollution levels based on the chemical properties, which can include phosphate and nitrates. Rivers are a very important water source used for human activities and ecosystems, which include the following activities: drinking, recreation, irrigation, laundry, construction work and sanitation [5]. However, the quality of some surface water can be affected by both physical and chemical parameters through natural and human activities [5,6]. Water pollution can be from anthropogenic sources, which include direct waste disposal, industrial effluent discharge, agricultural practices (pesticide and fertilizer usage), and improper sanitation, creating environmental problems faced by most developing countries [5,6]. Anthropogenic activities tend to introduce various forms of pollution that pose various risks to human health and the environment [5,6]. Physicochemical properties, nutrient levels, particulate matter, and microorganisms are common contaminants found in river water. Physicochemical properties such as phosphate, nitrate, magnesium, and chloride are known to harm human health, including gastrointestinal issues, neurological disorders, carcinogenic effects, and birth defects [5,7]. Much research has been done thus far, particularly highlighting the distribution of certain physicochemical characteristics of silt in rivers [8,9], but there is some information about the physicochemical characteristics of the Orisa River. This study, therefore, assessed the sediment samples for the distribution of the physical and chemical properties. The study aimed to assess the distribution of physicochemical properties of sediments from the Orisa River in Omu-Aran, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Description of Study Area

The study area was in Omu-Aran, which was in Nigeria's Kwara State's southern region. This settlement is native to the area and is located 564 meters above sea level at 8°8'00"N latitude and 5°6'00"E longitude [10,11]. This place has a tropical climate. During the rainy season, there is a significant amount of rainfall, whilst the dry season sees relatively little rain. The average annual temperature and yearly precipitation in Omu Aran are 24.9 °C and 1273 mm, respectively [10,11]. In Omu-Aran and the surrounding areas, the most common soil types are clayey, sandy, or gravely in texture, with a profile depth ranging from 3.5 to 5 m and a reddish-brown or brownish-grey colour. Migmatite or quartzite makes up the primary minerals [10,11].

2.2. River Orisa

The River Orisa flows through a number of settlements, including Aran Orin, Rore, Omu-Aran town, and other areas of Omu-Aran before emptying into the River Niger. The River Orisa is a significant source of water for Kwara State, which is located in north-central Nigeria. This river originates in Osun State and forms a border with the Aran-Orin Hills in Kwara State's Irepodun Local Government Area. Table 1 shows the Sampling Location Description. naturally from loosely or poorly compacted deposits. Along with providing the community with drinkable and irrigation water, the river also deposits farming-friendly fertilizer along its banks, especially in the rainy season and during floods [12,13,14,15]. This is before the river empties into the River Niger; its whole range is roughly 300 km from its source.

2.3. Collection of Sediment Samples

Quintuplicate sediment samples were obtained in the ratio of thirty (30) sediment samples collected once a week for three weeks from four sampling points and a control location. Using a portable Ekman grab sampler, 200 g of riverbed sediment was collected at a depth of 0 to 5 cm. The samples were packaged and labelled appropriately according to their location. The soil samples were pulverised, air-dried, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh screen. They were then stored in sterile polythene bags and labelled suitably concerning the five distinct locations, which are Aran-orin, Bovas area, FRSC area, Rore area and control which as shown in Table .1 describing the coordinate positions respectively before being stored at room temperature for the laboratory analysis [11]. The physicochemical properties of the sediments were ascertained by taking the labelled soil samples to Landmark University's Environmental Engineering Laboratory. Plate 1 shows the labelled soil sample collected from the River Orisa, while Plates 2 to 5 show the sampling locations.

Table 1: The Description of the Sampling Points along the River

Sampling points	Site location names	Location coordinate (Latitude, longitude)
Point A	Aran-Orin	N 727898 E 899129
Point B	Bovas area	N 727886 E 889118
Point C	FRSC area	N 707855 E 899065
Point D	Rore area	N 727849 E 899035
Point E	Control	N 727736 E 898852

Plate 1: Labelled soil sample collected from the River Orisa

Plate 2: Landmark University Sampling Point

Plate 3: Aran orin sampling point

Plate 4: FRSC Omu-Aran sampling point

Plate 5: Rore sampling point

2.4. Determination of Physicochemical Parameters

The standard analytical process previously outlined in the literature review was used to analyse the different parameters [12]. The temperature of the sediment was observed using a thermometer [13]. The pH of the sediment was determined in water using a Hanna pH meter [14]. The electrical conductivity and total dissolved solids of the sediments were determined using a HACH conductivity meter [15]. Phosphate, nitrate, magnesium, and chloride were determined using the Palin test Photometer 7100, and reagents were used for each [5,16].

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using the SPSS program Version 25.0, and an ANOVA was performed to evaluate the characteristics of all groundwater samples collected from all sampling stations. Duncan's multiple range comparison tests were performed to ascertain the difference between the average values of parameters measured at various locations using a 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$). Descriptive statistics were used to display all of the data, and correlation was performed to assess the relationship with the parameters and with the national guideline limits established by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) [16,17]. Plates 6 and 7 show the pH and Palin test photometer.

Plate 6: pH meter

Plate 7: Palin test Photometer 7100

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physical Properties of the Soil Sample

Physical analysis of sediment samples for the River

3.1.1 Temperature

Figure 1 shows the bar chart for temperature levels ranging between 27.13 ± 0.05 °C to 27.77 ± 0.05 °C, with the highest and lowest readings recorded at the FRSC area and Aran-orin, respectively. The temperature values varied considerably, so that in ascending order we have Aran-orin, Rore area, control Bovas area and FRSC area. There was no significant difference in the ranges because it was moderate, and the water temperature remained within the acceptable limit of 25–50 °C. The average temperature of the various locations shows no significant relationship. The implication of sediment in rivers can elevate water temperatures through multiple pathways. Sediment absorbs solar radiation, heating up and transferring warmth to passing water. It also reduces light penetration into the water, altering the amount of solar energy reaching the riverbed and contributing to warmer water temperatures, particularly in shallow areas [19]. Additionally, sediment can modify river flow patterns and depth, creating conditions where water warms more rapidly, especially in slower-moving or shallower sections. Furthermore, sediment carries nutrients that stimulate algal blooms, which might rise as a result of a longer seasonal window of high water temperatures, rising to maximize photosynthetic productivity by absorbing light [20]. To manage high water temperatures effectively, it is crucial to implement sediment management strategies. These include reducing erosion and sedimentation through land-use practices, restoring riparian vegetation to stabilize riverbanks, and enhancing overall watershed health. These efforts aim to mitigate the indirect impacts of sediment on water temperature and sustain suitable conditions for aquatic ecosystems.

3.1.2. pH

Figure 2 shows the bar chart for pH levels ranging between 6.78 ± 0.06 to 7.38 ± 0.03 , with the highest and lowest readings recorded at the FRSC area and Rore area, respectively. The pH values varied considerably, so that in ascending order we have the Rore area, Control, Aran-orin, Bovas area, and FRSC area. There was no significant difference in the ranges because it was moderate, and the sediment pH remained within the WHO acceptable limit of 6.5 to 8.5. The pH values show a significant relationship. The implication of pH profoundly impacts biological processes, environmental stability, and industrial operations. High pH can degrade aquatic ecosystems and hinder

enzyme function, while low pH poses health risks and damages infrastructure [6]. Balancing pH is essential for sustaining life, optimizing production, and preserving ecosystems.

Figure 1: Temperature in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

Figure 2: pH in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

3.1.3 Electrical conductivity

Figure 3 shows the bar chart for electrical conductivity, ranging between 2.76 ± 0.07 to 12.42 ± 0.03 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, with the highest and lowest readings recorded at the control and FRSC areas, respectively. The EC values varied considerably, so that in ascending order, we have Control, Rore area, Bovas area, Aran-orin and FRSC area. The values of the EC differed significantly, with the value of FRSC being higher than that of the others, although they were still within the WHO's acceptable range of 1000 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$. The electrical conductivity (EC) shows no significant relationship [22,23]. The implication is that human activities like swimming and washing clothes occur in the FRSC area, Omu-Aran, downstream of the river. According to [24], EC is a measure of the total dissolved substances in water, as well as the dissolved ionic components of magnesium and sodium. The results showed that there was extremely little dissolved salt content in the water samples. There won't be any negative effects from humans drinking the water.

Figure 3: Electrical conductivity in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

3.1.4. Total dissolved solids

Figure 4 shows the bar chart for total dissolved solid levels ranging between 1.45 ± 0.29 to 8.71 ± 0.04 mg/L, with the FRSC region and control recording the highest and lowest levels, respectively. The total dissolved solids values varied considerably, so that in ascending order we have control, Bovas area, Aran-orin, Rore area and FRSC area. The values of the TDS differed significantly, with the value of the FRSC area being higher than that of the others, as shown in Figure 4, but they remained within the acceptable limit of 300 mg/L. The TDS values show no significant relationship. The implication is that TDS is made up of minute amounts of dissolved organic materials and inorganic salts in water. TDS quantifies the amount of organic and inorganic substances that are dissolved in water. The amount, concentration, or level of TDS in the water can all have an impact on how much pollution has harmed the aquatic environment [15,21,27]. This is because TDS changes the flavour, colour, and smell of water while simultaneously making it lighter and more permeable. It is a useful measure of water quality. Elevations in total dissolved solids (TDS) render water unsuitable for drinking or agricultural irrigation, reduce photosynthetic efficiency, and raise water temperature [25].

Figure 4: Total Dissolved Solids in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

3.2 Chemical Properties of the Soil Sample

Chemical analysis of soil sediments for the River Orisa is shown in Figures 5 to 8.

3.2.1. Chloride

Figure 5 shows the bar chart for chloride levels ranging between 11.83 ± 1.72 to 28.17 ± 1.72 mg/L, with the lowest and highest readings recorded at the control and FRSC areas, respectively. Chloride values varied considerably, so that in ascending order we have Control, Bovas area, Rore area, Aran-orin, and FRSC area. The chloride values varied considerably, but they remained within the acceptable limit of 250 mg/L. The values of the chloride show no significant relationship. Chloride levels serve as indicators of water pollution from sewage. Possible sources of contamination include road salt runoff, synthetic fertilizer use, and landfill leachate [21]. High chloride concentrations can harm plant life in horticulture and agriculture, as well as impart an unpleasant taste to drinking water [26]. Elevated chloride levels in river water samples may stem from human activities such as sweating and urination in the water (the chemical composition of human sweat and urine) [21].

Figure 5: Chloride in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

3.2.2. Phosphate

Figure 6 shows the bar chart for Phosphate concentrations ranged between 0.05 ± 0.23 to 1.6 ± 0.21 mg/L, with the lowest and highest recorded at the Control and Aran-orin area, respectively. Chloride values varied considerably, so that in ascending order we have Control, Rore area, Bovas area, FRSC area and Aran-orin. Phosphate concentrations varied considerably, and as Figure 6 illustrates, the Aran-orin area value was much higher than the others and still under the WHO's allowable limit of 3 mg/L. Phosphate (PO_4) standard solution (3 mg/L) is used to prepare standards [27]. The values of phosphate show no significant relationship. The implication is that high concentrations of phosphate can lead to potential consequences, such as eutrophication or algal blooms, leading to contaminated drinking water sources, deteriorated leisure activities, and hypoxia [28].

3.2.3 Nitrate

The bar chart in Figure 7 displays the range of nitrate concentrations, which were measured in the FRSC and Aran-orin areas, respectively, with the lowest and highest values recorded at 0.43 ± 0.03 to 2.73 ± 0.04 mg/L. The FRSC area, Rore area, Bovas area, Control, and Aran-orin are the areas in ascending order due to the significant variation in nitrate values. The nitrate values varied greatly; the value for aran-orin is much higher than the others, as seen in Figure 7, while the values for the control and roach area are within the same range, as shown in Figure 7, and they were below the 50 mg/L WHO acceptable limit. The nitrates values show no significant relationship. The implication is that nitrate levels could cause blue-eyed syndrome in children and pregnant women [29]. Surface waters rarely contain much nitrate unless sewage effluents severely contaminate them. The ultimate oxidation of ammonia is nitrate, which is produced mostly by nitrifying bacteria in soil and water and can only

exist in environments with adequate oxygen. When nitrates are released into receiving water in an appropriate setting, they promote excessive algal bloom, which lowers the quality of the stream. Additionally, high nitrate levels can contribute to eutrophication [30].

Figure 6: Bar chart for phosphate in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

Figure 7: Bar chart for nitrate in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

3.2.4 Magnesium

The magnesium levels ranged from 0.01 ± 0.00 to 2.94 ± 0.06 mg/L, as shown in the Figure. 8, with control and Aran-orin exhibiting the lowest and highest values. Due to the wide range of magnesium readings, the following areas are arranged in ascending order: Control, Rore area, Bovas area, FRSC area, and Aran-orin. Although the magnesium readings varied greatly, they were still within the 50 mg/L WHO tolerable limit. The values of magnesium show no significant relationship. The implication of Magnesium inside water bodies comes from various forms of sediments, which can include sewage and industrial waste. Magnesium is the most abundant cation in the human system. It is regulated by the intestines, the bones, and the kidneys [31]. It prevents the production of crystals and is absorbed by a passive paracellular process in the ileum and distal jejunum, which reduces the risk of kidney stone formation, but processing in excess amounts can cause diarrhoea that can be accompanied by nausea and abdominal cramping [32].

Figure 8: Magnesium in sediment samples collected from the sampling points

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusion

The sediment samples from four different locations around the vicinity of the Orisa River have been investigated for possible contamination of their physicochemical parameters and have been compared with the World Health Organization (WHO). It was discovered that the mean values of the physicochemical properties were observed to be within limits when compared to the WHO standard.

4.2 Recommendations

It is therefore recommended that regular and periodic monitoring of the physicochemical parameters of the sediment samples should be carried out to ensure compliance with the regulatory standards.

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